

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF TAXATION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. Commercial banks in the world are the main link in today's economic growth. Banks receive their main profit in the form of interest and non-interest. In addition, commercial banks own high-value property and land. The above-listed income is considered an object of taxation of commercial banks. This article is about the taxes paid by commercial banks in Uzbekistan and their role in the structure of state budget revenues. It is also written about the tax burden on commercial banks in Uzbekistan and the share of the shadow economy.

Keywords: Direct taxes, object of taxation, tax base, tax burden, hidden economy, state budget, interest income.

Introduction. The complexity of the global financial system, the process of digitization and global financial integration are expanding the scope of banking activities. At the same time, the relevance of tax policy has increased, and the issue of providing stable and transparent income to state budgets remains relevant. According to the World Bank's Global Economic Prospects report published in 2023, "Global tax revenue from banks is expected to increase by 5% in 2022." Also, according to the report, "effective bank tax policy plays an important role in ensuring inclusive economic growth." Thus, an effective tax mechanism serves to ensure stability in the banking sector, increase financial transparency and strengthen economic justice. Therefore, improving the mechanism for taxing commercial banks is a relevant topic on a global scale today, and is of great importance for the sustainable development of the economy and the effective formation of the state budget. Currently, the issue of improving the mechanism of taxation of commercial banks is very relevant in international practice. In particular, researchers are studying issues such as determining the optimal level of tax benefits and deductions, taking into account the complex financial activities of banks, as well as expanding the tax base, identifying methods of tax evasion and aggressive tax planning by banks, assessing their economic impact and improving mechanisms for detecting and preventing these processes, increasing financial transparency and strengthening tax control through digital systems, increasing the efficiency of interstate information exchange and tax control systems, the impact of tax policy on the banking sector, the impact of this policy on the state budget and economic stability.

Methods. The study used the dialectical approach, induction, deduction, analysis and synthesis, systematic analysis, comparative analysis, statistical analysis, and other methods.

Results. Improving the mechanisms for taxing commercial banks in Uzbekistan is important for diversifying the economy and reducing the financial gap. This will increase the stability of the banking system and, accordingly, increase investment attractiveness, which will contribute to development. The importance of banks in the economy in the country is increasing, including the need to "reorganize their work in a new way and turn them into modern investment and commercial structures that implement promising projects and present them to entrepreneurs as ready-made businesses, not just credit centers." These changes will certainly stimulate the development of the real sector, improve the investment climate, create new jobs, and ensure economic growth. The effective implementation of these tasks largely determines the relevance of research aimed at developing scientific solutions to problems and obstacles in this area. The impact of tax policies on commercial banks is reflected in several important areas of the economic system. Such a tax burden, on the one hand, affects the activities and capital structure of banks, and on the other, it affects financial stability and broad macroeconomic indicators. Therefore, a deep understanding of the mechanisms of this impact is crucial for ensuring a balance between effective tax policy design, stimulating economic growth, and rational revenue generation. An analysis of international taxation practices for commercial banks reveals a variety of approaches, each with its own strengths and challenges. The best practices presented in this study serve as a valuable guide for regulators in developing effective tax systems that support financial stability, encourage rational banking practices, and stimulate economic growth.

Discussion. The share of profit tax paid by commercial banks in total profit tax revenues has increased by 1.8 times over the past 4 years. Also, as a result of the increase in the volume of operational leasing of terminals by commercial banks to business entities, the exemption from VAT of deposit boxes and banking services with a fixed value from 2022, this tax share has increased, and the dynamics of a decrease in the share of property tax in total property tax revenues to the budget can be observed. This, in turn, is explained by the fact that as a result of the implemented tax reforms, starting from January 1, 2019, all business entities, including legal entities with a turnover (revenue) of up to 1 billion soums, will be required to pay property tax, land tax, and water resource use tax. In recent years, the gradual reduction in property tax rates for legal entities, including commercial banks, has significantly reduced the share of this type of tax in total tax revenues. In particular, as a result of the reduction of the rate from 5 percent to 2 percent in 2019, and to 1.5 percent by 2022, there has been a sharp decrease in the amount of property tax paid

by banks. At the same time, it is noted that although the volume of total tax payments continued to grow, changes in the share of revenues from certain types of taxes led to certain changes in the structure of the tax burden. In particular, despite the reduction in the profit tax rate from 22% to 20% in 2019, the growth of bank profits and the abolition of tax incentives on profit tax ensured the growth of this tax revenue.

In previous years, certain incentives were established for commercial banks in paying profit tax, which allowed them to apply differentiated tax rates depending on the share of long-term investment financing in the bank's loan portfolio. However, this procedure was discontinued from January 1, 2020, these incentives lost their legal force, and profit tax was established in a single procedure for all banks. The above analysis of total tax revenues to the state budget and tax payments by commercial banks shows that the type of tax that accounts for a large share of tax revenues and, at the same time, is more complicated in terms of calculation than taxes paid by commercial banks is profit tax. The complexity of the calculation procedure for profit tax is due to the fact that it involves several processes in calculating the tax base and the correct determination of the composition of deductible and non-deductible expenses, as well as the application of tax benefits.

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